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VISION

The vision of the journals is to provide an academic platform to scholars all over the world to publish their novel, original, empirical and high quality research work. It propose to encourage research relating to latest trends and practices in international business, finance, banking, service marketing, human resource management, corporate governance, social responsibility and emerging paradigms in allied areas of management. It intends to reach the researcher's with plethora of knowledge to generate a pool of research content and propose problem solving models to address the current and emerging issues at the national and international level. Further, it aims to share and disseminate the empirical research findings with academia, industry, policy makers, and consultants with an approach to incorporate the research recommendations for the benefit of one and all.

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SR. NO.	PARTICULAR	PAGE NO.
1.	AN INVESTIGATION OF INDIAN EDUCATION IN JAPAN XU Hui	8-18
2.	A STUDY ON NON-GOVERNMENT PRIMARY TEACHER EDUCATORS IN THEIR DIFFERENT DIMENSIONS OF ORGANIZATIONAL CLIMATES IN WEST BENGAL Goutam Maiti	19-30
3.	LINGUISTIC ANALYSIS OF DISCOURSES IN ECONOMICS: SURVEY, ISSUES AND INSIGHTS Dr. K. Shanmugan, Baria Bhagirath Prakash	31-53
4.	PREVENTION OF COMPLICATIONS OF VARICOSE VEINS OF PELVIC ORGANS IN WOMEN OF REPRODUCTIVE AGE N.K.Dustova, D.B.Hafizova, V.Z.Jalolova, Raxmatova M.R	54-59
5.	BETI BACHAO BETI PADHAO: A STEP TOWARDS WOMEN EMPOWERMENT IN HARYANA MS. Payal Lamba	60-66
6.	MEMORY IMPAIRMENT AMONG PEOPLE WITH SUBSTANCE DEPENDENCE Swathy mol P. S, Joycy Jolly, Dr. Seena M. Mathai	67-73
7.	ROLE OF GREEN HRM IN BUSINESS Dr Meghana V P, Dr K Pramod Gonchkar	74-81
8.	CYRILLIC ALPHABET LETTERS IDENTIFICATION WITH THE HELP OF ARTIFICIAL NEURONS Iskandarova Sayyora Nurmatovna	82-91

9.	LIFE INSURANCE CORPORATION OF INDIA: A CRITICAL ANALYSIS Dr. U. Prabhakar Reddy, Prof. C R Reddy	92-99
10.	ASYMMETRIC RESPONSE OF FOREIGN CAPITAL VOLATILITY IN NEW ECONOMY-A TIME SERIES ANALYSIS Sandip Nandi	100-115
11.	PROFITABILITY ANALYSIS OF A MICRO AND PROPRIETARY ENTERPRISE - A CASE STUDY OF NAGAS ELASTOMER WORKS Dr. Venkateswararao. Podile, N.Janardhanarao, Dr. Ch. Hema Venkata Siva Sree	116-127
12.	HERMENEUTIC INTERPRETATION OF THE CATEGORY OF "AVESTO" AND UPANISHADS TASHKENT STATE INSTITUTE OF ORIENTAL STUDIES Shakirova Nadira Dadoyevna	128-136
13.	MAHARAJA HARI SINGH'S REFORMS AND THEIR IMPACT Dr. Nazakat Hussain	137-141
14.	IMPACT OF PSYCHOLOGICAL CAPITAL ON ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOR: A STUDY OF CLERICAL EMPLOYEES Zarreen Zaheer	142-146
15.	THE ROLE AND PLACE OF AGRO CLUSTERS IN IMPROVING THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF WATER USE IN THE REGION Prof. A.T.Kenjabaev, A.O Sultonov	147-151
16.	OPTIMIZATION OF THE TOP ORDER OF THE INDIAN TEST CRICKET TEAM Richa Saxena, Raghav Agarwal, Rounak Varma, Saachi Sethi, Prateek Upadhyay, Prerit Chaudhary	152-159
17.	THE IMPORTANCE OF THE REGION'S SOCIO-ECONOMIC POTENTIAL OF THE TOURISM MARKET Gavhar Khidirova	160-168

18.	GARO HILLS AUTONOMOUS DISTRICT COUNCIL: ISSUES AND PROBLEMS Sengat Agitchak Marak	169-176
19.	A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON SELF-ESTEEM AND ASSERTIVENESS AMONG ADOLESCENT GIRLS STUDYING IN SINGLE SEX AND CO-EDUCATIONAL SCHOOL OF MOHALI AND ROPAR DISTRICT (PUNJAB) Neha Sharma, Bharat Pareek, Rupinder Kaur	177-183
20.	CURRENCY AND DIAGNOSTIC CRITERIA OF RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS IN PATIENTS OF SENIOR AGE GROUPS Sh. Sh.Tillaeva, M.N.Badritdinova, A.U.Soliev, Sh.M.Akhmedova, M.A.Sharipova	184-188
21.	FACTORS AFFECTING CUSTOMER TO SHOP ONLINE: A STUDY IN INDIAN CONTEXT Dr. Jaipal Rathod, Dr. D.V.Srinivas Kumar	189-207
22.	A REVIEW ON SLUMS IDENTIFICATION AND POLICIES IN URBAN PUNJAB, INDIA Amandeep Kaur, Gaurav Kumar	208-215
23.	A STUDY ON CATEGORY-WISE PRODUCTION, DOMESTIC SALES AND EXPORT OF AUTOMOBILE INDUSTRY IN INDIA Nagamani.K.N, Dr. A. Muthusamy	216-227
24.	RANGING AND LIVING MASS OF KARAKUL LAMBS SUR OF TURTKUL FACTORY TYPE IN THE CONDITION OF THE NORTH-WESTERN KYZYL KUM Urimbetov A.A.	228-233
25.	APPLICATION OF INDICATORS FOR IDENTIFYING CLIMATE VULNERABLE AREAS IN SUB-TROPICAL REGIONS OF INDIA Surendra Singh, Sanatan Nayak	234-251
26.	URBANISATION IN MADYAMGRAM - A STUDY ON THE PATTERN OF EXPANSION OF THE URBAN BUILT UP AREA AND THE SUITABILITY OF THE URBAN SERVICES Chayanika Choudhury, Prof.Sankar Majumder	252-266

27.	PROBLEMS IN RESTORATION AND RECONSTRUCTION OF HISTORICAL LIVING HOUSES AND THEIR SOLUTION, CASE OF SAMARKAND INSTITUTE Anvar Aymatov	267-273
28.	MEASURING CUSTOMERS PERCEPTION IN THE TELECOM INDUSTRY: AN INDIAN PERSPECTIVE Mr. Amit Naru, Dr.V.K.Kaushik, Dr.Samridhi Tanwar	274-285
29.	THE WAY AHEAD WITH CASHLESS MEDICAL TREATMENT- A STUDY ON AWARENESS OF CASHLESS MEDICAL TREATMENT AMONG CORPORATE EMPLOYEES R. Amruthamma, Dr. T.Aswathanarayana	286-296
30.	RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN MENTAL HEALTH AND SOCIAL COMMITMENT AMONG STUDENT TEACHERS OF B.ED P. Menaha, Dr. P. Janardhana Kumar Reddy	297-303
31.	ROLE OF STAKEHOLDERS IN GREEN PRACTICES OF HOTEL INDUSTRY: EVIDENCE FROM GREATER HYDERABAD MUNICIPAL CORPORATION (GHMC) STAR HOTELS Dr. Arakhita Behera	304-319
32.	AN OVERVIEW OF TRAINING ACTIVITIES IN TEXTILE AND APPAREL MANUFACTURING SECTOR Shipra, Dr Aneet, Dr Amandeep	320-327
33.	A COMPARATIVE STUDY TO MEASURE ANXIETY, DEPRESSION AND LIFE SATISFACTION OF CARDIAC AND NONCARDIAC PATIENTS OF KOLKATA CITY Abdul Gani, Farha Hakim	328-342
34.	ATTITUDE OF STUDENTS TOWARDS PROJECT BASED LEARNING OF ECONOMICS IN SECONDARY SCHOOL Ms. Mona Bhumij	343-348
35.	A STUDY OF CUSTOMER SATISFACTION W.R.T.BANK OF MAHARASHTRA IN PUNE DISTRICT Dr. Vishal Waman Wagh, Dr.Deepa Tahalyani	349-356

36.	ASSESSMENT OF NDVI AND NDWI OVER BURHISUTI WETLAND OF ASSAM USING IRS LISS III DATA Krishna Das	357-365
37.	FACTORS AFFECTING CUSTOMERS' WILLINGNESS TO PURCHASE ORGANIC FOOD IN INDIA: A LOGISTIC REGRESSION MODEL Dr. Sama Vijayalakshmi, Mr. Samala Nagaraj	366-373
38.	WOOL-BEARING PRODUCTIVITY OF LOCAL GOAT OF KARAKALPAKSTAN ToreshovaAmina Ubbiniyazovna	374-377
39.	RETAIL CUSTOMER TOWARDS MODERN RETAILING AN EMPIRICAL STUDY Dr. P. Chakrapani, Dr.T.Ravindra Reddy	378-383
40.	DIFFERENT CATEGORIES OF SOFTWARE: SOFTWARE THAT PLAY PIVOTAL ROLE IN RESEARCH WORK Rupinder Kaur	384-391
41.	PRIORITY WAYS OF THE FOOD SAFETY SUPPORT IN UZBEKISTAN Mamadiyorov Olimjon Umarovich	392-396
42.	UNLEASHING THE POWER OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND PERSONALITY Muskan Kaura	397-403
43.	LANGUAGE AS A REPRESENTATIONAL TECHNOLOGY: A QUALITATIVE SOCIOLOGICAL REVIEW IN CASE OF HIV/AIDS RELATED STIGMA STUDY Joydeb Patra, S.A.H.Moinuddin	404-418
44.	PLANNING THE MOVEMENT OF MOVING MOBILE ROBOTS IN A CHANGING ENVIRONMENT R. Siddikov	419-426
45.	IMPACT OF INFRASTRUCTURE IN URBAN DEVELOPMENT: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF INDIA AND CHINA Dr. O. P. Miglani, Ms. Arti Rani	427-434

LIFE INSURANCE CORPORATION OF INDIA: A CRITICAL ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

Safety and security has become the prime concern of everybody in the society. India has considerably developed economy and a section of people still feel unsafe and insecure. Insurance has come up as an important financial service in most part of the world. In fact, insurance is considered as one of the important segments in the economy for its growth and development. Life insurance is an important form of social safety and security. The insurance industry has witnessed many phases of a giant shape after privatisation of insurance industry. The result of foreign direct investment of 49 per cent in insurance has increased competition for the Life Insurance Corporation of India. In the recent years, the public has made criticism on the performance of LIC of India at it has failed to achieve the objectives for which it came into being. The criticism is due to the advent of many insurance schemes like – linked bank deposit, postal insurance and high rate of interest in the money market.

KEYWORDS: *Life Insurance, Financial Performance, Social safety, Insurance Penetration, Insurance Density*

INTRODUCTION

Social Safety and security has become the prime concern in the life of every-individual in the society. India has a developed economy and still a section of people feel unsafe and insecure. A thriving insurance sector is of vital importance to every modern economy in terms of encouraging the savings habit and providing a safety-net to people; perhaps the most importantly generating the long-term invisible funds for infrastructure building of the country. Insurance is a major among the service sectors contributing to the financial savings of the household sector of the country and such savings are channelized into various investment avenues. [1] The insurance business was carried on by 154 Indian and 16 non-Indian insurance companies, and 75 provident societies in 1956. The financial crisis and the economic down turn severely, impacted the sales of single premium and unit-linked products. Resultantly, profitability of insurers deteriorated in 2008 due to low investment yields, high cost of guarantees and low revenues from asset management. However, solvency was collision and access to capital became difficult. In the recent years, the public has made criticism on the performance of LIC of India at it has failed to achieve the objectives for which it came into being. The criticism is due to the advent of many insurance schemes like – linked bank deposit, postal insurance and high rate of interest in the money market.

By passing the Life Insurance Act of 1956, the Indian Parliament has nationalised the insurance business and created the Life Insurance Corporation of India on September 1, 1956 with the objective of spreading life insurance more widely to reach all insurable persons in the country at reasonable cost. On the occasion of Life Insurance Corporation's nationalisation, the then Prime Minister Jawaharlal Nehru said thus: The nationalisation of life insurance is an important step in our march towards a socialistic society; its objective will be serving to the individual and the State. We require life insurance to spread rapidly all over the country and to bring a measure of security to our people. An attempt is made to analyse the parameters such as insurance penetration, insurance density, number of policies, sum assured business, claims settlements of Life Insurance Corporation of India in this competitive age.

The main feature of insurance players is cash flow constantly whereas the payout is deferred which makes them the biggest investment in long-gestation infrastructure development projects in all development aspects of nation. Huge fund collected by way of premium from millions of policyholders and the amount retained by the insurance players as solvency fund to meet the unforeseen contingencies which invariably need investment as per prudential norms.

Life insurance has also undergone significant rapid changes from implementation of reforms in the country which has a most remarkable record. Group insurance of employees through their employers has shown swift progress during the past five decades. Great Depression of the 1930's with less than one-tenth of one per cent of policyholders' funds lost during this period. Many life-insurers in the late 1960's were expanded their corporate structure including mutual funds with widened financial services.

The Life Insurance Corporation of India was the sole player in the life insurance industry for the last five decades. The entry of private insurance players and allowing foreign direct investment in insurance industry affects the performance of LIC of India in the near future. The private insurance players have become joint ventures between major business houses or banks in India and renowned international insurance giants. [2] At this juncture, it became necessary to appraise the financial and operating performance of LIC of India as it supposed to compete with its

counter parts within country and abroad. Thus, the LIC public sector giant which never faced competition earlier now has to compete with the private insurance players who boast of the rich and long experience of their partners from the developed countries of the world. It becomes imperative at this instance to apprise of the analytical performance LIC of India in terms of (a) business expansion, (b) market penetration and market density and (c) investment.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Ravi N Kadam critically examined the importance of life-insurance in risks management and performance competitors for LIC of India focusing the measure of insurance business on the basis of gross premium and net premium income. [3] On the descriptive ratio performance of LIC of India from 2008-09 to 2012-13 in a competitive market environment, Prachi Agnihotri has thrown light on the overall performance evaluation of LIC of India. He observed the performance of life insurance is consistent and suggested to have more service standards to maintain the market value of products.[4] K. Ramanathan in his research paper studied the cost control efficiency of LIC of India through Data Envelop Analysis (DEA) and observed the score rank is high and maintained consistency compared to the private insurance companies.[5] Sonal Nena in his study justified the performance of LIC of India so to include that “ the LIC of India is doing good job, managing the products and related marketing strategies effectively”. [6]

LIFE INSURANCE CORPORATION OF INDIA

The Life Insurance Corporation of India established with Headquarter in Mumbai in 1956 and is the largest life insurance company in India owned by the Government of India. It has acquired almost monopoly power in solicitation and sale of insurance policies in India and also extended its activities in 12 foreign countries with motto of catering to the insurance needs of Non-Resident Indians. The enforcement of New Economic Reforms in 1991 coupled with the formation of Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority Act of 2000 and started issuing licences to the private insurers. It is only insurance company belonging to the public sector now has to compete with several other corporate entities of its kind which often are heavyweight in the country and Multinational Life Insurance Brands in themselves. India with its huge middle class households has exhibited growth potential for the insurance industry. Saturation of markets in many developed economies has made the Indian market more attractive even for the global insurance sector. The insurance market in India has witnessed the dynamic changes including the entry of a number of global insurers.

LIC has also leveraged on telecommunications and information technology to set up call centres, internet enabled services, information kiosks etc. With an intention of providing quicker and better services to the policyholders, approximately 97 per cent of the total branches of LIC have front end computerization for giving on-line service to policyholders. In addition to this, New Delhi, Chennai, Bangalore and Mumbai have installed Metro Area Network (MAN) and interactive Voice Response System (IVRS). A specialized position known as Customer Relations Executive to ensure a customer base with is loyal and satisfaction in achieving to:

- Delight the customers with steadfast loyalty to the organization
- Reduce the number of customer grievances and service delivery failures
- Impart customer centric culture across the organization
- Increase the customer base

NEW MILLENNIUM GROWTH

Advent of automobile age, mass production techniques of modern industry, introduction of air plane, railroads expansion and changing the social consciousness of an affluent society and more closely affected the rise of insurance as a major business of new millennium. Development in casualty insurance is rise of workmen's compensation insurance business and also growth of automobile insurance to insure millions of drivers and automobiles. Laws of negligence have increased the need for many other forms of liability insurance. High medical costs and loss of income have skyrocketed health insurance to a multibillion-rupees towards the casualty of insurance field. The modern concept of business creates customers though sounds simple but has great implications. The customer is not only the buyer but whose loyalty towards the organization has greater invisible force. It implies customer is considered a pivotal factor for the growth and survival of the services sector.

ANALYSIS OF DATA

Life Insurance Corporation of India is doing yeoman services of insurance services in India. By providing insurance, it is securing the value of human life and gives security to the person having insurance policy. The growth of Life Insurance Corporation of India can be assessed in terms of number of policies issued, sum assured and annual premium, claim settlement and commission paid. Data on number of policies with sum assured, annual premium, commission paid to Agents and Development Officers and settlement of claims are presented in Table 1. The performance of LIC of India is analysed with the help of compound growth rate by using the regression function of $Y = ab^t$. The compound growth rate is equal to $(\text{Antilog of } b - 1) \times 100$. This is written as: $\text{Log } Y = \text{log } a + \text{log } b (t)$. Where, $Y = \text{Variable}$, $t = \text{time variable}$, a and $b = \text{parameters}$.

TABLE 1 PERFORMANCE OF LIC OF INDIA
(₹ In crore) (Policies in lakh)

Year	No. of Policies	Sum Assured	Annual premium	Claims settled		Commission paid
				No.	% claims settled to filed cases	
2000-01	196.57	124772	8852	11667	3.70	3256
2001-02	224.91	192569	16009	14359	1.90	4595
2002-03	242.67	179504	12504	17062	1.12	4999
2003-04	264.56	198707	12541	19607	0.91	5734
2004-05	239.74	187132	11861	23642	0.80	6245
2005-06	313.86	288522	15635	28473	0.83	7095
2006-07	382.21	303231	24489	36486	0.68	9169
2007-08	376.13	279693	24438	37206	0.96	9568
2008-09	358.00	395755	20982	40706	1.03	10033
2009-10	386.51	43478	26193	44129	1.11	12110
2010-11	370.57	47311	26483	47556	1.14	13309
2011-12	357.36	51076	26189	51914	1.12	14036
2012-13	366.53	51525	25693	54945	1.19	14768
2013-14	344.91	557092	31904	58108	1.21	16681
2014-15	359.52	508458	23112	41443	0.96	15092
2015-16	411.31	557700	25350	42222	0.99	15478
2016-17	421.57	561150	25507	43486	0.96	20866

2017-18	431.58	572044	26004	44330	0.97	21275
Mean	333.99	283318	21319	36519	1.20	11351
Growth	119.40	149.0	193.8	280.2		554.2

Source: LIC of India, Various Annual Reports

Table 1 shows the components performance of Life Insurance Corporation of India. The number of insurance claims settled is 11667 lakh in 2000-01 which increased to the highest number position of ₹ 44330 lakh in 2016-17 which a rise by 379.96 lakh policies or 2.26 per cent. Commission is the percentage of premium paid to an insurance agent by insurer as compensation for completing the sales. The commission has increased from ₹ 3256 crore in 2000-01 to ₹ 21275 crore in 2016-17. Likewise, the annual premium from ₹ 8852 crore in 2000-01 to ₹ 26004 crore in 2016-17, policies sum assured from ₹ 124772 crore in 2000-01 to ₹ 572044 crore in 2016-17 and number of policies from 196.57 lakh in 2000-01 to 210.58 lakh in 2016-17. An increase in 2016-17 to the position of 2000-01 is accounted by 553.41 per cent, 62.43 per cent, 358.47 per cent and 7.13 per cent respectively for the above components respectively. Table analysis for the data during the period from 2000-01 to 2017-18 discloses that the average number of insurance policies, sum assured, annual premium and commission paid is accounted for 333.99 lakh, ₹ 283318 crore, ₹ 21319 crore and ₹ 11351 crore respectively.

An inference that could draw from the analysis of Table 1 is that the progress of sum assured has increased significantly followed by annual sum assured and number of life-insurance policies. The achieved growth is accounted for 119.40 per cent, 149.0 per cent, 193.80 per cent, 280.2 per cent and 554.40 per cent for number of policies, sum assured, annual premium and commission paid respectively. The increased progressive performance in claims settlement is much higher followed by annual premium and sum assured compared to other components enlightening the LIC of Corporation effective measures in ensuring social safety as well as social security.

INSURANCE PENETRATION AND DENSITY

The potential performance of insurance sector is assessed through two factor-analyses namely insurance penetration and insurance density. Ratio of premium underwritten in a given year to the gross domestic product is termed as insurance penetration. As GDP per capita rises, it is expected that individuals will purchase more insurance. The insurance penetration measures the level of insurance activity relative to the size of the economy. Insurance density is defined as the ratio of premium underwritten in a given year to the total population. Data analysis of insurance penetration and density are presented in Table 2.

TABLE 2 INSURANCE MARKET PENETRATIONS AND DENSITY

Year	Insurer penetration	Insurer density
2005-06	4.10	33.20
2006-07	4.00	40.40
2007-08	4.00	41.20
2008-09	4.60	47.70
2009-10	4.40	55.70
2010-11	3.40	49.00
2011-12	3.17	42.70
2012-13	3.10	41.00
2013-14	2.60	44.00
2014-15	2.78	44.62

2015-16	2.72	45.08
2016-17	2.75	45.12
Mean	3.47	44.14

Source: Annual Reports, LIC of India

Table 2 discloses the insurance penetration in India for 2005-06 to 2016-17. The life-insurance penetration is 4.10 per cent in 2005-06 whereas it 2.75 in 2016-17. The insurer density is 33.20 in 2005-06 and 45.12 in 2016-17. During the period from 2005-06 to 2016-17, the average life-insurance penetration is worked out at 3.47 and 44.14 for insurer density. An observation that could make is that though the insurance penetration has increased at a diminishing by 0.63 in 2016-17 to that of 2005-06 position in spite of having a good premium record observed from Table 2. In terms of insurance density, it is 33.20 in 2005-06 and 44.14 in 2016-17 which implies more number of people got insured on account of popularity of the life insurance scheme not only as safety and security but also awareness of savings too among the people to become policyholders.

INVESTMENT

The motto of Life Insurance Corporation of India is to become a nation builder. It has mobilised the funds invested by the people in the form of life insurance premium for the socio-economic benefit of community at large. The Corporation has deployed its funds to the best advantage of the policyholders and the community as a whole. The national priorities as well as obligation of reasonable return to the policyholders are the main broadened criteria of investment by the LIC of India. Therefore, the insurer needs to make a sound investment frame for healthy growth of business on the business principles and to safeguard the interests of policyholders too in terms of payment of assured amount plus bonus, etc., and plough of profit into the insurer for steady growth and sustenance. By means investment in the Government and infrastructure and the social sector certainly help a smooth growth of economy. Tap funds mobilisation and invest on sound lines for health growth is a strategic approach to the LIC of India. Data on investments made by the LIC of India is presented in Table 3.

TABLE 3 LIC INVESTMENTS

(₹ In crore)

Year (1)	Central Govt. (2)	State Govt and other guarante ed marketab le securities (3)	Infrastructure and Social sector investment						Grand Total (10)
			Housing (4)	Power (5)	Irrigation etc (6)	Transport (7)	Others (8)	Total (9)	
2005-06	236959 (66.12)	58928 (31.68)	19807 (31.68)	29740 (47.57)	8288 (13.26)	725 (1.16)	3954 (6.32)	62514 (17.44)	358401 (100.00)
2006-07	272498 (66.38)	64285 (15.66)	22451 (30.44)	37881 (51.37)	7500 (10.17)	1516 (2.05)	4398 (5.96)	73746 (17.96)	410529 (100.00)
2007-08	297943 (63.50)	89234 (19.02)	24325 (29.66)	41120 (50.13)	6649 (8.11)	1154 (1.41)	8774 (10.69)	82022 (17.48)	469199 (100.00)

2008-09	318673 (60.12)	110697 (20.88)	34185 (33.93)	48090 (47.71)	6022 (5.97)	7218 (7.16)	5274 (5.23)	100789 (19.00)	530159 (100.00)
2010-11	147859 (55.87)	33045 (39.44)	4482 (5.35)	76167 (90.90)	25 (0.03)	686 (0.82)	2427 (2.90)	83787 (31.65)	264691 (100.00)
2012-13	1308887 (92.64)	83746 (5.93)	4222 (20.83)	10995 (54.26)	36 (0.18)	-	5012 (24.73)	20265 (1.43)	1412898 (100.00)
2014-15	1776939 (94.77)	63158 (3.37)	7392 (21.21)	15840 (45.44)	33 (0.09)	77 (0.22)	11515 (33.03)	34857 (1.86)	1874954 (100.00)
2016-17	2318952 (97.26)	44262 (1.86)	6414 (30.56)	298 (1.42)	34 (0.16)	13859 (66.04)	382 (1.82)	20987 (0.88)	2384201 (100.00)
Mean	834839	68419	15410	32516	3573	3605	5217	59871	963129

Source: LIC of India, Various Annual Reports

Figures in brackets in columns 4, 5, 6, 7 and 8 are percentages to total figure in columns 9; and in columns 2, 3 and 9 are percentage to figure in column 10

Table 3 unfailing reveals the Life Insurance Corporation of India as premier insurance insurer and has shown interest in protecting the policyholders' interest in terms of safe and security for their premium paid by means of investment in the Central Government, State Governments and infrastructural and social sector investment. It has invested a sum of ₹ 236959 crore in 2005-06, ₹ 58928 crore, ₹ 62514 crore in Central Government, State Governments and infrastructure and social sector investment respectively. The corresponding figures in 2016-17 are ₹ 2318952 crore, ₹ 44262 crore and ₹ 20987 crore in 2016-17 respectively for the above. An increase in terms of grand total amount is accounted for by ₹ 2025800 crore or by 465.23 per cent. Total investment in infrastructure in social sector is accounted for ₹ 62514 crore in 2005-07 while the figure is in 2016-17 is ₹ 20987 crore which means a decrease of ₹ 41527 crore or by 66.43 per cent. Investment growth of LIC of India is at an increasing trend in the securities of Central Government and State Governments, and also in infrastructure investment like housing and power followed decreasing trend in irrigation.

CONCLUSION

As a primary function, insurance with aim of protection with safety and security by assessing the risk and sharing the same with risk-sharing should be yardstick of LIC of India which goes beyond its primary purpose of spreading the risk and thereby minimising the loss. Besides, the basic functions, the subsidiary responsibilities should offered so as to prevent loss and also aid to the economic development of the country through the investment of funds under the international prudential norms. Claims settlement should be made easy and within specific time limit. Huge premium collection from million-policyholders and amount retained by them as solvency fund to meet the unforeseen contingencies should invariably be invested in income results-oriented securities adopting the sound financial management norms.

A strategic role of LIC of India in investment should 6: 2: 2 in Central Government and State Government and Business respectively which combine the principle of safety and return so that the insurer should become a strong-hold agent in the country. In addition social security and safety, the LIC should take a provision of health-insurance scheme at least the policyholders with additional premium for the certain specified health diseases so that the entire gamut of social security, social safety and health coverage within the ambit of Life Insurance Corporation of India. Then only the catalytic role insurance would shape the nation's socio-economic

development and thereby insuring the economic safety and social security of people with happiness for their well-being and welfare. Added, the insurer ought to implement good customers' relation to emanate CRM as it helps expand business, streamline and automate the process with facility of instant information and facts without a hassle.

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Dated : 30-11-2018

Dear

DR. U. PRABHAKAR REDDY, PROF. C R REDDY

I am very pleased to inform you that your article/research paper titled **LIFE INSURANCE CORPORATION OF INDIA: A CRITICAL ANALYSIS** has been published in **Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research (AJMR)** (UGC approved journal No. 47638) (ISSN: 2278-4853) (Impact Factor: SJIF 2017 = 5.443) Vol.7, Issue- 11, November, 2018.

The scholarly paper provided invaluable insights on the topic. It gives me immense pleasure in conveying to your good self that our Editorial Board has highly appreciated your esteemed piece of work.

We look forward to receive your other articles/research works for publication in the ensuing issues of our journal and hope to make our association everlasting.

Thanking you once again

With Best Regards

Dr. Esha Jain
Publishing Editor
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2. The articles passed through screening at this level will be forwarded to two referees for blind peer review.
3. At this stage, two referees will carefully review the research article, each of whom will make a recommendation to publish the article in its present form/modify/reject.
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